

Academic Literacies in Portuguese as an Additional Language: reflections from a bibliographic review /

Letramentos Acadêmicos em Português como Língua Adicional: reflexões a partir de uma revisão bibliográfica

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ABSTRACT

This study aims to analyze publications derived from research on academic literacies within the context of Portuguese as an Additional Language (PAL), in order to discuss recent developments in the field. The period between 2018 and 2024 was selected for the collection of articles, dissertations, and theses from Google Scholar, the CAPES Journal Portal, and the Brazilian Digital Library of Theses and Dissertations (BDTD). Each study was analyzed in terms of its objectives, methodology, participants, and findings. The search resulted in seven works — three journal articles, one master's dissertation, and three doctoral theses — which, by addressing diverse perspectives on academic literacies, reveal varied themes and insights into students' learning processes. The studies include international students who use PAL in their academic practices and teachers who examine their pedagogical approaches through the design of teaching materials and instructional units.

KEYWORDS: Academic Literacies; Portuguese as an Additional Language; International Students; Mapping.

RESUMO

O presente trabalho tem como objetivo analisar publicações resultantes de pesquisas sobre letramentos acadêmicos que investigam o contexto do Português como Língua Adicional (PLA) a fim de discutir o desenvolvimento atual na área. Foi escolhido o período entre 2018 a 2024 para a coleta de artigos, dissertações e teses, nas plataformas Google Acadêmico, Portal de Periódicos da CAPES e Biblioteca Digital Brasileira de Teses e Dissertações (BDTD). Analisou-se os objetivos, a metodologia, os participantes e os resultados obtidos em cada relato de pesquisa. A busca resultou em sete trabalhos,

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sendo três artigos, uma dissertação e três teses, que, ao apresentarem as possibilidades de estudos em letramentos acadêmicos, apresentam resultados diversificados em termos de temáticas, bem como sobre o processo dos alunos participantes. Os trabalhos contam com participantes migrantes internacionais que utilizam o PLA em suas práticas acadêmicas e com professores que investigam suas práticas por meio da construção de materiais e unidades didáticas.

PALAVRAS-CHAVE: *Letramentos Acadêmicos; Português como Língua Adicional; Estudantes internacionais; Mapeamento.*

1 Introduction

The institutionalization of Portuguese as an Additional Language (PAL) teaching in Brazilian universities began between the 1980s and 1990s, with the creation of programs designed to offer courses, train teachers, and conduct research in the field (Schlatter, Bulla & Costa, 2020). This development is part of a significant transformation that has taken place in Brazilian higher education over the past decade (Moraes, Azevedo & Catani, 2014; Pinto & Larrechea, 2019), also characterized by the growing presence of international students (Sousa & Sousa Filho, 2024). At present, extension programs remain the predominant format, and PAL courses primarily serve exchange students (Marques & Schoffen, 2020).

The increasing recognition of Portuguese as an object of scientific, methodological, and educational initiatives, combined with the rising number of international students at Brazilian universities (Molsing & Lopes-Perna, 2014) and the implementation of PAL programs targeting this audience (Santos, 2023), reflects the intensification of globalization processes and the expansion of academic exchange through bilateral agreements and cooperation initiatives such as the Undergraduate and Graduate Student Exchange Programs (PEC-G and PEC-PG). These programs “support students from Latin American and African countries” and constitute “a response to the Brazilian government’s foreign policy efforts to strengthen ties with these two regions” (Neves & Martins, 2016, p. 116). Such initiatives have played a crucial role not only in increasing the number of international students but also in promoting deeper engagement between the Portuguese language, Brazilian culture, and the local academic environment (Ferreira, 2020).

The Federal University of Pelotas (UFPeL) contributes to the internationalization of Brazilian higher education through initiatives such as interinstitutional agreements and academic mobility programs (Universidade Federal de Pelotas, 2018). In 2020, UFPeL established its Language Policy

(LP) to meet internationalization demands by fostering multilingualism and interculturality. The LP emphasizes the importance of “valuing the knowledge, use, and vitality of languages in general”, adopting a plurilingual and democratic approach that promotes mutual understanding, exchange, and collaboration among different “languages, dialects, cultures, ethnicities, and communities” (Universidade Federal de Pelotas, 2020, p. 1).

Regarding PAL-related internationalization actions, UFPel’s Language Policy encourages: a) welcoming, training, and supporting speakers of other languages in PAL; b) promoting teaching, research, and outreach activities in PAL; c) offering PAL courses for speakers of other languages and d) institutionalizing PAL within the University’s Center for Languages and Communication (Universidade Federal de Pelotas, 2020). These actions are part of the institution’s broader efforts to strengthen PAL initiatives, acknowledging their growing relevance (Damasceno & Selbach, 2021; Ramires & Selbach, 2023; Santos et al., 2023; Silva et al., 2023).

Given the growing internationalization process in PAL within Brazilian higher education, it becomes essential to investigate how academic literacies¹ are configured in this context. From this perspective, Vignoli, Ferrarini-Bigareli, and Cristovão (2021) conducted a study to map practices and perspectives of undergraduate program coordinators at public universities in Paraná state regarding academic literacies in PAL. This mapping of actions and demands, as emphasized by the authors, was fundamental for developing practical proposals focused on academic literacies in additional language. As they note, this research illustrates “one of the ways used to investigate contextual needs” (Vignoli; Ferrarini-Bigareli; Cristovão, 2021, p. 31). Additionally, the authors show that demands related to the Study Skills model (Lea; Street, 2014), particularly those concerning reading, writing and grammar, were most frequently mentioned by the coordinators who responded to the questionnaire.

Similar to the investigation conducted by Vignoli, Ferrarini-Bigareli, and Cristovão (2021), the ongoing research project conducted at UFPel entitled *Academic Literacies in Portuguese as an Additional Language at UFPel: Mapping Practices and Needs* (Selbach, 2023), seeks to identify

¹ Following Fiad (2002, p. 24), we use the term *academic literacies* in lowercase plural “to indicate that there is not just one academic literacy [...]”. In contrast, the capitalized term *Academic Literacies* refers to a specific theoretical approach or model — the Aclits approach — distinguishing it from other theoretical frameworks, following the same convention that Lea and Street use when proposing their three models: Study Skills, Academic Socialization, and Academic Literacies.

practices and needs related to Academic Literacies in PAL within the university's institutional context and community.

As more international students arrive at the university, there is an increasing need to understand their academic practices and to promote familiarity with the discursive and cultural conventions of the Brazilian academic environment. This challenge is therefore not limited to testing PAL proficiency but extends to fostering awareness of the norms, expectations, and conventions of each respective community of practice (Lave & Wenger, 1991).

This research aims to contribute to the advancement of studies in the field of PAL and support the development of future internationalization initiatives at UFPel, articulated with research, teaching, and extension activities. As part of the bibliographic review conducted within this project, the present article seeks to provide an overview of current research on Academic Literacies in PAL in Brazil, offering theoretical and methodological insights to inform the ongoing investigation at UFPel.

Situated within the field of Applied Linguistics, this article maps publications (articles, master's dissertations, and doctoral theses) on Academic Literacies in PAL, analyzing the research objectives, methodologies, participant profiles, and key findings of these works.

The next section discusses the concept of Academic Literacies, followed by an overview of this study's methodological framework.

2 Academic literacies

Research on Academic Literacies emerged as an interdisciplinary field in the 1980s, drawing on Sociolinguistics, Applied Linguistics, and the New Literacy Studies (Lillis & Scott, 2007). In the context of the expansion of higher education in the United Kingdom—marked by increasing cultural, social, and linguistic diversity—educators began to challenge the dominant discourse that attributed an alleged decline in academic standards to newly admitted students, framing diversity itself as a problem (Lillis & Scott, 2007).

Within this context, Lea and Street (1998) adopted an anthropological perspective to study academic writing through the lenses of power relations, ideology, and situated practices — core dimensions that define the Academic Literacies approach (Lillis & Scott, 2007). This framework

proposes an empirical investigation into the nature of academic writing across diverse contexts and examines what “doing academic writing” means to those involved (Lillis & Scott, 2007, p. 9).

In higher education, learning involves students’ adaptation to new ways of understanding and organizing knowledge (Lea & Street, 1998). The ideological model of Academic Literacies proposed by Lea and Street (1998) departs from perspectives that naturalize academic conventions, instead adopting a sociocultural approach to literacy that avoids reducing writing to a binary classification of good versus poor performance.

Academic Literacies encompass a typology of writing practices that integrates three interrelated perspectives or models: (1) Study Skills, (2) Academic Socialization, and (3) Academic Literacies. These models are not mutually exclusive but rather nested within one another: Academic Socialization incorporates Study Skills within a broader process of acculturation, while Academic Literacies subsume both, offering a more comprehensive understanding of academic writing as a social practice shaped by identity, power, and institutional dynamics (Lea & Street, 1998). These relationships are illustrated in *Figure 1*.

Figure 1: Academic Literacies.

Source: Selbach (2018, p. 52) based on Lea and Street (1998).

The Study Skills model conceptualizes literacy as a set of general, transposable abilities that students are expected to acquire (Lea & Street, 1998). It seeks to “fix” learning problems through a remedial, skills-based approach grounded in behaviorist psychology and training methodologies, treating writing as a purely technical or instrumental task. From this perspective, the cognitive and

social effects of literacy are assumed to occur autonomously (Street, 2003 [2001]). The linguistic theory underlying this model focuses on the “surface features” of writing—such as spelling and grammar. A central critique of this approach lies in its treatment of writing as a decontextualized, generic skill detached from the conceptual and disciplinary thinking specific to each field (Street, 2010a). Refining the notion of “skill” while incorporating greater attention to social context and broader learning processes led to the development of the Academic Socialization model (Lea & Street, 1998).

The Academic Socialization model positions tutors and supervisors as responsible for introducing students to the norms and conventions of academic “culture.” Although this model advances beyond the *Study Skills* approach by recognizing cultural and contextual dimensions of learning, it has been criticized for its oversimplified representations of academia and academic writing (Lea & Street, 1998). It tends to portray the university as a homogeneous culture with stable practices and rules that can be learned to gain institutional access, while writing is viewed as a transparent medium for conveying meaning. Lea and Street also point out the model’s limited theoretical discussion of institutional practices, processes of change, and the power relations embedded in academic life.

In contrast, the Academic Literacies model views students’ writing and learning as socially situated practices intrinsically linked to epistemological and identity-related issues. This perspective offers a more context-sensitive understanding of literacy, recognizing the complex relationship between discourse, knowledge, and power (Street, 2003 [2001]). As Street (2010b, p. 546) observes:

[The Academic Literacies model] is the one that best takes into account the nature of students’ textual production in relation to institutional practices, power relations, and identities; in short, it manages to encompass the complexity of meaning-making, unlike the other two models.

The ideological model of Academic Literacies highlights variation where the autonomous model assumes uniformity—for instance, in aspects such as punctuation, spelling, or pronunciation. It is described as *ideological* rather than *pragmatic* or *cultural* because it “draws attention to the unequal and hierarchical nature of literacy in practice” (Street, 2003 [2001]). From this perspective, discourse and power are seen as constitutive elements of academic institutions (Lea & Street, 1998).

Academic Literacies emerged at a pivotal moment in the history of higher education in the United Kingdom, prompting critical reflection on how an inclusive and equitable university system should examine the semiotic assumptions underlying its dominant literacy practices (Lillis, 2021). However, as Lillis (2021) argues, these issues extend far beyond the British context: researchers and educators around the world continue to grapple with similar challenges in their own institutional settings.

In the context of PAL, the Academic Literacies framework—rooted in the tradition of the New Literacy Studies (Lea & Street, 1998)—emphasizes the social and contextual nature of reading and writing practices in higher education. From this perspective, the use of Portuguese in academic settings goes beyond language acquisition, encompassing engagement in specific social practices and the negotiation of power and identity within diverse academic communities across Brazilian universities (Santos & Macedo, 2021). This approach thus provides a more comprehensive and contextualized understanding of the challenges and processes involved in developing academic literacy in PAL contexts.

Developing Academic Literacies in PAL therefore involves more than mastering linguistic structures; it requires adapting to the cultural, epistemological, and institutional dimensions of Brazilian academia, enabling international students to participate meaningfully in these new environments (Santos & Macedo, 2021; Stumpf, 2021). In this process, drawing on the full linguistic repertoires of both Brazilian and international students can foster multilingualism and affirm students' linguistic and cultural identities.

According to Schlatter, Bulla, and Costa (2020), teacher education must include the development of specific competences for multilingual instruction, emphasizing the implementation of pedagogical methodologies that value and integrate the linguistic diversity present in classrooms. The authors argue that continuous professional development and responsiveness to students' needs are essential for effective and inclusive teaching:

Teacher education [...] presupposes collective discussions aimed at understanding the potential and responsibilities of language education and of acting as a teacher in specific contexts and in dialogue with peers. A curriculum should foster challenges and debates that encourage reflection on political and ideological values, historically situated meanings associated with

different discourses, and possibilities for ethical, autonomous, and creative intervention (Schlatter, Bulla & Costa, 2020, p. 500).

Against this backdrop, research on PAL for academic purposes remains relatively scarce (Stumpf, 2021). In addition to the limited number of studies, there is a notable shortage of teaching materials specifically designed for this context, which often compels educators to create their own resources or make substantial adaptations to materials originally developed for native speakers of Portuguese.

Regarding international students' perspectives on Academic Literacies in PAL, Santos and Macedo (2021) identified a range of study strategies employed by these learners. Among the most common practices were seeking assistance from Brazilian classmates and professors, participating in tutoring programs, and searching for vocabulary online. The researchers also observed that international students tended to prefer printed materials when reading academic texts, indicating a preference for more traditional ways of accessing information in this context. According to the authors, the challenges faced by international students go beyond Portuguese language proficiency and involve "limited familiarity with reading and writing practices specific to the academic field" (Santos & Macedo, 2021, p. 1).

In light of these findings, the next section outlines the methodological framework adopted in this study.

3 Methodology

Searches were conducted in Google Scholar, the CAPES Journal Portal, and the Brazilian Digital Library of Theses and Dissertations (BDTD) for articles, master's dissertations, and doctoral theses published between 2018 and 2024 that addressed Academic Literacies in the context of PAL. The six-year timeframe was established to include the most recent research published on the topic.

In Google Scholar, searches covered works published from 2018 to 2024 (up to the data collection date of June 14, 2024). In the *advanced search* field, the following terms (in Portuguese)

were used: *letramentos acadêmicos*, *português adicional*, and *estrangeiros* under “with all the words,” and *mapeamento*, *escrita*, and *oralidade* under “with at least one of the words.”

Since the platform does not yet allow searches for the current year, a search was carried out on June 18, 2024, in the CAPES Journal Portal for articles published between 2018 and 2023. In the *advanced search* field, the terms (in Portuguese) *letramentos acadêmicos* and *português adicional* were used.

Finally, searches in the BDTD were conducted on June 18, 2024, covering works published from 2018 to 2024 and using the same terms (in Portuguese) as those applied in the CAPES Journal Portal search — *letramentos acadêmicos* and *português adicional*.

4 Results

After excluding works unrelated to the theme of Academic Literacies in PAL, the searches conducted across the three platforms yielded seven studies: one master’s dissertation and three doctoral theses from the BDTD, and three journal articles from the CAPES Journal Portal. Together, these works constitute the corpus of this review. The Google Scholar search, in turn, returned publications of various types—such as books, book chapters, and conference abstracts—and subjects outside the scope of this research. Therefore, these materials were not included in the corpus.

The main characteristics of the selected studies are summarized in Table 1, which organizes them chronologically and presents the authors, publication years, research objectives, methodological approaches, participants, and key findings.

Table 1 Authors, publication year, objectives, methodology, participants, and key findings

Study (Author/Year)	Objective(s)	Methodology	Participants	Key findings
Ferreira e Rollsing (2018)	To discuss theoretical and methodological	Qualitative research based on a bibliographic review	Not applicable	“Students’ objectives and needs, as well as the realities in which

	implications of discourse-genre studies for teaching Portuguese for Academic Purposes (PAL).	of theoretical constructs such as academic literacy, generic competence, discursive sphere, and discourse genres.		they are situated, should guide teachers' planning and classroom practices" (p. 853).
Cândido (2019)	To analyze teachers' narratives about the PEC-G Program and their experiences teaching PAL in the pre-PEC-G course.	Qualitative research using semi-structured interviews with teachers and analysis of interactions from in-person meetings and email exchanges.	Five PAL teachers.	The study identifies adversities faced by international students and highlights the potential of the PEC-G teaching context to foster teachers' critical-reflective development and the benefits of collaboration for teacher identity construction.
Carneiro (2019)	To analyze and describe the development of a PAL course aimed at the metapragmatic regulation of participants' positioning in oral and written interactions.	Qualitative research with a reflexive ethnographic approach, based on field activity records and compilation of writing files.	Immigrant students enrolled in a PAL course.	Students constructed reflective knowledge across distinct cultural contexts and used linguistic resources in academic writing as forms of resistance and challenges to institutionalized conventions.

Andrighetti (2020)	To propose a pedagogical design for teaching PAL for academic purposes.	Qualitative research through the analysis of (1) an instructional plan for a course focused on academic genres and (2) an academic reading and writing course, complemented by classroom observation and discussions with enrolled students.	International students enrolled in a Portuguese for Academic Purposes course.	Pedagogical goals include creating spaces for students to understand reading and writing practices in higher education and to analyze the oral and written productions required of them.
Fernandes (2021)	To investigate academic literacy practices of international students participating in academic mobility programs and enrolled in a PAL writing course.	Qualitative research analyzing: (1) questionnaires; (2) an instructional unit; (3) learning journals; (4) classroom recordings; (5) the use of the Translog-ll tool; and (6) students' final production of the academic abstract genre.	Five students from different countries.	Students had prior experience with academic reading and writing practices; however, when placed in a Portuguese language course, they tended to focus on systematic linguistic use rather than engagement with academic genres.
Fernandes (2022)	To characterize international students' representations of the genre academic abstract genre.	Diagnostic questionnaire collecting students' personal data, followed by analysis of the instructional unit developed in Module 3 and students' written learning journals.	Five students from different countries.	Students positioned themselves as interlocutors within a specific social environment. The study notes shortcomings in materials, activities, and pedagogical practice design.

Rodrigues (2024)	To examine the potential and implications of (trans)media literacy for learning and academic autonomy in Deaf education.	Qualitative exploratory approach employing a single-case study, combining semi-structured interviews and participant observation to collect narratives.	One Deaf undergraduate student in an English Studies program.	(Trans)media literacy in Deaf higher education involves challenges related to training, access, and linguistic and socio-semiotic resources, which affect students' ability to communicate effectively through this methodology.
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Source: Prepared by the authors of this article.

The analysis of the selected studies reveals a variety of themes, methodological approaches, and research objectives. Figure 2 illustrates the main themes, methodologies, and participant profiles of the studies analyzed, which are described below.

Figure 2: Themes and methodologies of the studies analyzed.

Source: Prepared by the authors.

Teaching experiences in a PAL course within the Undergraduate Student Agreement Program (PEC-G) were analyzed by Cândido (2019). The qualitative methodology involved semi-structured interviews with five teachers, supplemented by records of interactions from in-person meetings and email exchanges. In addition to the five PAL instructors in the pre-PEC-G course, participants included thirteen international students from various countries: two from Benin, one from Cameroon, seven from Ghana, one from Honduras, and two from Jamaica. By privileging the narratives of the teachers and the teacher-researcher herself, Cândido (2019) sought to understand perceptions regarding the PEC-

G and experiences in PAL teaching. The findings revealed several challenges faced by international students in their first year in Brazil, such as financial difficulties, problems with social interaction, limited institutional support for health-related issues, and cultural barriers, exacerbated by limited proficiency in Portuguese. These difficulties directly affected the teachers' practice, as instructors had to deal with such obstacles to ensure student learning. Furthermore, the study highlights the potential of the PEC-G teaching–learning context to contribute to teachers' critical-reflective professional development and the benefits of collaboration for the construction of teacher identity. The group's cultural and linguistic diversity prompted the teachers to reassess and adapt their pedagogical practices, seeking more effective strategies to meet students' needs and promote learning for all. The PEC-G context, therefore — with its challenges and specificities — encourages PAL teachers to re-examine their practices and develop new strategies to meet students' needs. In this context, collaboration among teachers creates a space for mutual learning and support, fostering reflection and the construction of a more critical teaching identity attuned to students' needs.

Also within the context of international cooperation and academic mobility programs, the development of a PAL course was examined by Carneiro (2019). Unlike Cândido (2019), Carneiro focused on the metapragmatic regulation of oral and written positioning in the interactions of Haitian students who arrived in Brazil through the Emergency Pro-Haiti Program, designed to enable them to complete undergraduate degrees at Brazilian universities. The methodology adopted included field notes, recordings of oral practices, and the compilation of a corpus of writing samples. The author participated in the students' initial reception, serving as a PAL instructor at the State University of Campinas (Unicamp), one of the institutions participating in the program. After the course ended, the students were directed to their undergraduate programs without continued Portuguese-language support. This situation led the author to design a specific PAL reading and writing course in response to the students' need to produce a final monograph. The course aimed to strengthen academic writing skills and deepen students' understanding of academic genres. Beyond developing the course, the author reflected on the integration process of students from cooperation and mobility programs with non-central countries into the Brazilian academic context. Drawing on Academic Literacies studies, the author investigated: (a) the students' difficulties with reading and writing practices; (b) how they learned about the discursive functioning of these practices; and (c) the potential for developing specific teaching

materials for PAL instruction with academic purposes. The findings reveal power relations underlying the dynamics of knowledge construction in reading and writing practices and in processes of developing reflective knowledge. These dynamics manifested, for example, (1) in the appropriation of knowledge by combining distinct cultures as a means of producing new understanding and (2) in the challenge to academic writing conventions through the use of Haitian Creole linguistic resources within the Brazilian academic context as an act of resistance.

Building on discussions about the development of PAL courses for academic purposes, Andrighetti (2020) presented a pedagogical design proposal for teaching PAL for academic purposes in her doctoral dissertation. Whereas Carneiro (2019) developed an emergency course for Haitian students, Andrighetti (2020) sought to broaden the opportunities for international students to engage with the diverse types of texts they encounter in academic contexts. To this end, she analyzed a teaching plan designed for a course centered on academic genres — both written and oral — alongside a PAL reading and writing course offered to international graduate students at a private university in southern Brazil.

The course aimed “to assist students and researchers from other universities abroad who are pursuing their studies at PUCRS through academic mobility programs” (Andrighetti, 2020, p. 106). The author underscores that PAL teaching contexts require the creation of spaces for reflection on language and culture. Such reflections should engage both the students’ language practices in their first languages (in semester 2017/1, the three participants were Spanish speakers from Spain, Peru, and Colombia) and their perceptions of how Portuguese operates linguistically and culturally, based on their own experiences.

The study therefore broadens the discussion on how cross-linguistic and sociocultural differences shape the texts students produce in PAL. Overall, the findings highlight the importance of creating pedagogical spaces that help students understand reading and writing practices in university contexts and analyze the oral and written productions required of them — such as abstracts, reviews, essays, articles, and oral presentations of academic work — while considering the production context, the social functions of texts, and disciplinary expectations regarding knowledge.

The theoretical reflections that underpin practical proposals such as Andrighetti’s (2020) are further developed in the study by Ferreira and Rollsing (2018). The authors examined the use of

discourse genres in the teaching of Portuguese for Academic Purposes (PAP) within the broader framework of PAL for exchange students at Brazilian universities. Their work presents a theoretical discussion based on a bibliographic review of four key concepts: (1) generic competence, (2) academic literacy, (3) discursive sphere, and (4) discourse genres, as discussed by Bakhtin (2016), Maingueneau (2013), Marcuschi (2008), and Street (2010, 2014). Ferreira and Rollsing (2018) aim to provide theoretical support for how these concepts can be mobilized by PAL teachers in their pedagogical practice “in order to promote the academic literacy of foreign students in producing spoken and written texts belonging to the genres of the academic discursive sphere” (p. 839). They highlight the importance of integrating discourse genres from a PAL perspective, seeking not only linguistic mastery but also the development of students’ discursive autonomy within academic environments. According to the authors, generic competence—developed through familiarity with discourse genres (Bakhtin, 2016) — is intrinsically linked to academic literacy (Street, 2010, 2014), which requires understanding the social function of texts and their contextualization in real literacy practices. The academic discursive sphere, in turn, includes specific genres that require explicit instruction, such as research articles, abstracts, and oral presentations (Marcuschi, 2008).

To illustrate the importance of moving beyond the teaching of linguistic structures, the authors draw on Bakhtin (2016), who observed that even individuals with command of a language face difficulties in certain fields of communication—an observation that underscores the need to consider the purposes and social functions of genres. Regarding the discursive sphere and its relationship with discourse genres and linguistic proficiency, the authors remind us that “knowing a language does not necessarily imply having the skills required to comprehend and produce texts belonging to a given genre or discursive sphere” (Ferreira & Rollsing, 2018, p. 848). From this perspective, it is essential to look beyond linguistic structures and attend to the purposes and social functions realized through genres. Ferreira and Rollsing (2018) conclude that the effectiveness of PAL teaching depends on addressing students’ needs, goals, and realities, encouraging pedagogical practices that foster critical engagement with the world and active participation in the academic sphere through writing. The aim, they argue, is to promote “a kind of teaching that awakens learners to a reading of the world and whose writing becomes part of the actions that move this world” (Ferreira & Rollsing, 2018, p. 850).

Drawing on these theoretical perspectives on discourse genres within a specific context, Fernandes (2020 [2022]) examined the academic abstract genre. The study sought to characterize the perspectives of five undergraduate students — from the United States, Finland, France, Italy, and Mexico — regarding the genre of the academic abstract. Methodologically, a diagnostic questionnaire was administered to investigate the international students' exposure to and use of Portuguese. An instructional unit (IU), designed by the author as the third of five course modules, was analyzed alongside the manuscripts and learning journals produced by the participating students. The findings indicate that the activities placed stronger emphasis on linguistic aspects than on sociocultural ones when addressing academic genres. According to the author, the overall impression is that the IU tended to prioritize textual work over social engagement with the genre. As he explains, “a partnership was envisioned between the text's author and the student-reader, guided by a social relation that would lead the latter to a value-based appreciation of the text and to reflection on the inseparable dimensions that constitute the genre” (p. 309). From this perspective, Fernandes (2020 [2022]) acknowledges that, although the instructional unit was successfully implemented, there were shortcomings in its overall development.

In a subsequent and broader study, Fernandes (2021) investigated literacy practices in PAL among international students through an instructional unit. Building on his 2020 [2022] study, the author analyzed the practices of five students from Finland, Italy, France, the United States, and Mexico, all enrolled in a PAL writing course linked to international and academic mobility programs. Methodologically, the study examined records from Module 3 of the PAL course taught by Fernandes in 2019, including: (1) a questionnaire administered at the beginning of the course to collect student background information; (2) an instructional unit designed for the writing module to assist both teacher and students in carrying out the activities; (3) students' oral and written learning journals documenting their learning processes and experiences throughout the course; (4) audio recordings of class sessions, which allowed students to express their perspectives during the course; (5) reports and written assignments produced as part of their familiarization with the Translog-II tool; and (6) the final version of the academic abstract, written using Translog-II after completing various academic writing tasks — including summaries, reviews, research projects, and oral presentations — across the course modules. The findings indicate that most students had some prior experience with reading and writing academic

texts, both at their home universities and at the Brazilian institution where the course was offered, the Federal University of Minas Gerais (UFMG). However, when participating in a Portuguese course, the students tended to focus on the formal structure of texts in their reading and writing, seeking to learn through the systematic use of language and surface-level features rather than through engagement with specific academic genres in the university context.

Expanding the scope of research on Academic Literacies beyond international students, Rodrigues (2024) investigated (trans)media literacy in Deaf education. The main objective of the study was to understand the potential and implications of (trans)media literacy for the academic autonomy of a Deaf student. Using a qualitative and exploratory single-case study design, the research followed one Deaf undergraduate student during her academic activities, combining semi-structured interviews and participant observation to analyze how engagement with multimodal materials shaped her learning experience. The findings reveal that the incorporation of multiple modes of communication — such as text, image, movement, and sound — fostered multimodality and enabled meaning-making beyond written and spoken forms. The student demonstrated the ability to integrate (trans)media literacy concepts into her academic practices, which contributed to her autonomy as a learner. The study also highlights the importance of accessibility and linguistic agency, emphasizing the need for careful attention to sign language interpretation and to the student's active intervention in cases of misinterpretation — both essential for developing academic autonomy. Rodrigues (2024) further underscores the empowering potential of (trans)media literacy in expanding Deaf students' opportunities for expression and participation in academic contexts.

The next section analyzes these studies, highlighting their contributions, gaps, and implications for the field of Academic Literacies in PAL, while also proposing directions for future research.

5 Analysis and Discussion

The reviewed studies address a range of themes, including teacher education and professional experiences in implementing PAL courses (Cândido, 2019), the design of a reading and writing course (Carneiro, 2019), and pedagogical frameworks for teaching PAL for academic purposes through discourse genres (Andrighetti, 2020).

The corpus also includes a literature-based reflection on discourse genres in the teaching of Portuguese for Academic Purposes (Ferreira & Rollsing, 2018), analyses of instructional units and of the academic abstract genre (Fernandes, 2021; 2022), and an investigation of (trans)media literacy in the learning process of a Deaf student (Rodrigues, 2024).

Methodologically, the studies are predominantly qualitative, employing diverse approaches such as literature review (Ferreira & Rollsing, 2018), semi-structured interviews (Cândido, 2019; Fernandes, 2021; 2022), ethnographic observation (Carneiro, 2019), analysis of instructional materials and classroom observation (Andrighetti, 2020; Fernandes, 2021; 2022), and case study (Rodrigues, 2024). The participants include PAL instructors (Cândido, 2019), international students (Fernandes, 2021; 2022), and a Deaf undergraduate student in Brazil (Rodrigues, 2024).

In terms of objectives, the studies range from theoretical reflections on discourse genres (Ferreira & Rollsing, 2018) to practical investigations into teachers' (Cândido, 2019) and students' (Fernandes, 2021; 2022) experiences. Some focus on the development of courses and instructional materials (Carneiro, 2019; Andrighetti, 2020), while others explore more specific dimensions such as metapragmatics (Carneiro, 2019) or (trans)media literacy (Rodrigues, 2024). This diversity of aims reflects the complexity and richness of the field, encompassing theoretical inquiry, pedagogical practice, learning experiences, and the specific challenges faced by different students' groups in academic contexts.

The findings, in turn, reveal the complexity of teaching and learning PAL in academic contexts, highlighting aspects such as the need to consider students' specific profiles and contexts in pedagogical planning (Ferreira & Rollsing, 2018), the challenges faced by international students (Cândido, 2019), and the implications of (trans)media literacy for Deaf learners (Rodrigues, 2024). The studies also emphasize the importance of teachers' critical-reflective development (Cândido, 2019) and the relevance of creating spaces for students to understand and analyze academic literacies — that is, reading and writing practices within the university context (Andrighetti, 2020; Fernandes, 2021; 2022).

The studies also demonstrate a shared concern with promoting approaches grounded in the Academic Literacies perspective, which align – to varying degrees – with the three models proposed by Lea and Street: Study Skills, Academic Socialization, and Academic Literacies. The works of Ferreira and Rollsing (2018), Andrighetti (2020), Carneiro (2019), and Cândido (2019) align most

closely with the Academic Literacies model, emphasizing the situated nature and social dimensions of academic reading and writing practices. These studies acknowledge the complexity and diversity of literacy practices within higher education, moving beyond technical skills to incorporate issues of identity, power, and authority in academic discourse.

Conversely, the studies by Fernandes (2021, 2022), although designed to engage with the Academic Literacies perspective, leaned more strongly toward the Study Skills and Academic Socialization models. This tendency suggests a greater focus on the technical aspects of writing and academic conventions, possibly without fully achieving the critical dimension proposed by the Academic Literacies model. The tension between technical and critical approaches highlights the ongoing challenge of balancing immediate demands for linguistic proficiency with the broader goal of developing critical awareness of academic practices.

Nevertheless, there is a growing concern among researchers with promoting Academic Literacies in a broader and more comprehensive manner, recognizing their importance for the success of international students within the Brazilian academic environment. A defining feature of the studies analyzed is their practical orientation, which extends beyond the theorization of concepts. The works demonstrate a strong commitment by researchers to applying theoretical constructs in real educational contexts, expressed through concrete pedagogical proposals, course implementations, the development of instructional units, and the design of teaching materials.

At the core of these studies and pedagogical proposals lies the concept of discourse genre, which serves as a guiding axis for much of the research and pedagogical intervention. This genre-based approach permeates multiple dimensions, including teacher education and professional development, the advancement of academic literacies among international students — particularly through the analysis of their textual production across genres — and the promotion of learner autonomy in Deaf education within higher education. Researchers in PAL are actively engaged in creating and evaluating pedagogical tools and methodologies that contribute to the teaching and learning of PAL. This practical orientation not only enriches the theoretical field but also provides valuable resources for educators and institutions working with PAL students, fostering innovative and context-sensitive approaches to teaching and learning in this specific domain.

6 Final Considerations

This study aimed to map and analyze publications (articles, dissertations, and theses) that investigate Academic Literacies within the context of PAL in order to understand how this theme has evolved in recent years.

The analysis of the studies revealed a wide range of themes addressed in PAL research conducted in academic settings. The works cover topics ranging from teaching experiences in PAL courses under the PEC-G program to pedagogical design proposals for PAL instruction with academic purposes. A significant emphasis was observed on the use and pedagogical mobilization of discourse genres, with particular attention to the academic abstract genre, examined through the development and implementation of specific instructional units. The design and implementation of courses, along with the creation of pedagogical proposals adapted to students' needs, emerged as recurrent themes reflecting the pursuit of innovative methodologies in PAL teaching. Additionally, some studies focused on more specific aspects, such as (trans)media literacy in the learning process of a Deaf student, highlighting a growing concern with inclusion in PAL education.

These findings — mostly derived from qualitative approaches — point to a dynamic and continually evolving research field that seeks to address contemporary challenges in teaching PAL within multicultural academic environments. As noted by Schlatter, Bulla, and Costa (2020, p. 494), the consolidation of PAL as a field “is an everyday process of creating and institutionalizing spaces that bring together groups of people attuned to the demands of their time and dedicated to developing qualifications for personal projects, professional profiles, and academic training areas.” This perspective is reflected in the studies analyzed, which demonstrate an ongoing commitment to the education and professional development of qualified practitioners as well as to the advancement of innovative pedagogical practices. Thus, the field of PAL stands not only as an area of academic research but also as a collective and institutional movement that addresses local needs while adapting to the evolving demands of an increasingly diverse and multicultural academic environment.

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